

Factsheets on solar PV locations in Switzerland

Description of production potentials, technical characteristics,
electricity costs, and environmental impacts

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Energy glossary

1 kWh (kilowatt-hour): A unit of energy equal to the electricity consumption of a typical light bulb of 10 Watt for 100 hours. 1 kWh is also the unit for which the electricity price is defined (ct./kWh). The electricity consumption of a typical Swiss household of four persons ranges between 3 000 – 4 000 kWh/year, depending on the type of dwelling. Information on the conversion of units can be found in the table below.

Unit	Equivalence
1 kWh (kilowatt-hour)	1 kWh
1 MWh (megawatt-hour)	1 000 kWh
1 GWh (gigawatt-hour)	1 000 MWh <i>or</i> 1 000 000 kWh
1 TWh (terawatt-hour)	1 000 GWh <i>or</i> 1 000 000 MWh <i>or</i> 1 000 000 000 kWh

kWp (kilowatt-peak): A unit of power that stands for the maximum output that a system can generate in ideal conditions (comparable to the maximum speed of a car). It is used to describe the size of PV panels. A rooftop PV system on a residential house has a capacity of 5-20 kWp, whereas ground-mounted solar PV parks can reach up to 100 MWp or even more.

Production potential by 2035: An estimation of how much electricity could theoretically be produced in Switzerland in the year 2035, expressed in TWh/year. It considers criteria of technical, legal, environmental, and economic feasibility, but excludes aspects of social acceptance.

Specific yield: Refers to how much electricity a solar PV panel can produce per unit of installed capacity over a certain period and is expressed in kWh/year/kWp. It is typically used to describe productivity, or, in other words, how much electricity solar PV panel produces in a specific location, relative to the panel's size or capacity.

Winter electricity production: The share (%) of the total annual electricity production that is produced in the winter half-year period (1st October – 31st March), when electricity demand is the highest and production the lowest. The higher the winter electricity production, the more the solar PV panel can contribute to securing a reliable supply and to reducing electricity imports in Switzerland.

Electricity costs: The costs of generating 1 kWh of electricity, expressed as ct./kWh (Levelized Cost of Electricity, LCOE). This includes the costs of investment, construction, operation, and decommissioning. It does not include taxes, grid charges or subsidies. In general, electricity costs decrease as the size of the PV system increases.

Grid integration and storage: Refers to the requirements and conditions of physically connecting the PV system to the transmission and distribution grids for transporting and/or storing the electricity from the production location to final consumers.

Maintenance: Refers to activities required to ensure that the solar PV system functions properly during its lifetime. This includes measures for cleaning, inspection and repairs of the equipment.

Expected lifetime and end-of-life: An estimation for how many years a PV panel can produce electricity until it must be replaced and the conditions for removing the equipment.

Impacts on land use and natural landscapes: Describes whether the deployment of solar PV at a certain location requires additional land use and its effects on natural landscapes.

Impacts on the environment and biodiversity: Describes how the deployment of solar PV at a certain location impacts the environmental surrounding, such as the local flora and fauna.

Solar photovoltaics (PV): A brief introduction

The key technology that generates electricity from sunlight is called solar photovoltaics (PV). A solar PV installation consists of several solar modules and can be installed anywhere where there is sun, such as on rooftops, façades or in open fields. The more sunlight, the more electricity can be produced (Figure 1).

Solar PV only produces electricity during the day when the sun shines and has lower production in winter due to fewer hours of sun. These daily and seasonal fluctuations can pose a challenge for the management of the electricity grid which needs to balance electricity demand and supply at all times. For this reason, electricity storage solutions such as batteries are often used in combination with solar PV, as it allows the excess electricity to be used during periods of low solar PV production. This ensures a more reliable and flexible supply.

Solar PV does not emit any direct carbon dioxide (CO₂) during operation, and it is considered a renewable, clean, and local electricity technology for replacing fossil fuel-based generation. Like any technology, the production of solar PV panels and their whole life cycle require energy and materials, such as silicon, aluminum, copper, and glass. This also results in various environmental impacts, including CO₂ emissions. Nonetheless, by now, a solar PV panel produces more electricity and saves more CO₂ emissions over its lifetime than was required to manufacture it. At the end-of-life, a large part of the materials can be recycled.

Figure 1: Simplified illustration of how solar PV works. The generated electricity can either be used directly to cover electricity demand or stored for later use, for example, with a battery.

The role of solar PV for the energy transition in Switzerland

Solar PV is rapidly growing and currently it is already the second largest source of renewable electricity in Switzerland after hydropower. In 2022, solar PV accounted for 7% of the national electricity production (3.8 TWh) (Figure 2). The potential of solar PV is very large across the entire country with considerable expansion potential for the future (Figure 2). For this reason, solar PV is considered a key technology for reaching Switzerland's long-term energy and climate objectives.

In September 2023, the Swiss Parliament adopted a new target in the “*Mantelerlass*” process which aims to reach 35 TWh/year of additional renewable electricity production by 2035 (excl. hydropower). This policy also aims to reduce the domestic electricity supply gap in winter, which would decrease the need for electricity imports and improve the security of supply in Switzerland.

It has been estimated that solar PV must contribute 30 TWh/year to reach the federal target. While this will require a rapid national PV deployment, there is still flexibility in deciding *where* the new installations should be located. There are two main types of locations to be considered: solar PV in built areas (e.g., rooftops, infrastructure) and in open spaces (e.g., fields, mountains, lakes). The overall performance of a solar PV system is largely determined by its location (e.g., production potential, costs, and environmental impacts) and is presented in the following section by means of performance indicators.

Figure 2: a) The electricity production in Switzerland in 2022 (source: BFE 2022); b) Specific yield of solar PV in Switzerland, expressed in kWh/year/kWp. The redder the color, the more electricity can a solar PV panel produce, relative to its size (source: Solargis 2022).

Summary of performance indicators for solar PV locations in Switzerland

Performance evaluation scale*		Rooftop and façade PV	Infrastructure PV	Agri PV	Floating PV	Ground-mounted alpine PV
	Rather good					
	Rather poor					
	Poor					
Production potential by 2035						
Specific yield						
Winter electricity production						
Electricity costs						
Grid integration and storage						
Maintenance						
Lifetime and end-of-life						
Impacts on land use and natural landscapes						
Impacts on environment and biodiversity						

* Mixed colors indicate a range of values between two levels and/or that a clear rating could not be determined.

Rooftop and façade PV

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Technology description

Rooftop and façade PV refers to the installation of solar panels on rooftops or walls of residential, commercial, or industrial buildings.

Benefits and challenges

Rooftop and façade PV is a mature, common technology that allows for an efficient double use of land, combining already built spaces with renewable electricity production. This minimizes negative impacts on the environment and the landscape. However, not all rooftops or façades are suitable for PV deployment due to limited space or poor sun exposure of the building (e.g., northward orientation, shading, chimneys, windows). Deployment is also challenged by investment costs, which are not affordable to all homeowners, whereas utility companies may not be interested in operating small, decentralized PV systems.

Current production

In 2022, PV on rooftops and façades in Switzerland produced around 3.8 TWh. This equaled 6-7% of Switzerland's total electricity production. Current electricity production with PV therefore comes almost exclusively from systems on rooftops and façades.

Performance indicators

Production potential by 2035	Approximately 26 TWh of electricity could be produced per year from rooftop (20 TWh/year) and façade PV (6 TWh/year) by 2035 in Switzerland. This would be equivalent to 45% of the annual Swiss electricity production in 2022 (58 TWh).
Specific yield	In the Swiss Midlands and pre-Alps, where most urban settlements are located, a solar PV panel with a capacity of 1 kWp can produce 1150-1350 kWh of electricity per year. This is up to 25% lower than for solar PV located in the Swiss Alps.
Winter electricity production	Approximately 30% of the electricity from rooftop PV is produced during the winter, making it less suitable for closing the winter electricity gap. PV on façades can reach higher shares of winter production thanks to the vertical installation but they generate lower amount of electricity throughout the whole year.

<p>Electricity costs</p>	<p>Electricity costs for rooftop and façade PV have been estimated at 7-25 ct./kWh. The costs vary depending on the sun exposure and the size of the installation. In general, smaller installations on individual residential homes have higher electricity costs than ground-mounted PV systems. This is due to economies of scales of larger systems, which profit from lower unit costs (e.g., at installation, maintenance).</p>
<p>Grid integration and storage</p>	<p>Rooftop and façade PV systems can easily be integrated into the existing grid or operate independently, meaning that they only produce electricity for the on-site demand and use batteries for storage. Many individual and decentralized panels may, however, at times cause instability issues for the grid because of a lack of centralized control.</p>
<p>Maintenance</p>	<p>While small rooftop and façade PV systems on individual one-family houses can typically be accessed rather easily, undertaking maintenance activities for larger systems on multi-story buildings or installations on steeply pitched roofs can be more challenging.</p>
<p>Expected lifetime and end-of-life</p>	<p>The expected lifetime of rooftop and façade PV is about 30 years. The removal of the PV systems typically does not cause any permanent damage to buildings.</p>
<p>Impacts on land use and natural landscapes</p>	<p>The installation of rooftop or façade PV requires no additional land use, as PV systems are integrated into buildings. Similarly, the visual impacts on natural landscapes are very low.</p>
<p>Impacts on environment and biodiversity</p>	<p>Rooftop and façade PV typically does not directly interfere with the surrounding ecosystems and natural habitats of flora and fauna. The negative impacts on the environment and biodiversity are therefore minimal.</p>

Infrastructure PV

<p>Technology description</p>	<p>Infrastructure PV refers to the installation of solar PV panels on any type of existing infrastructure, such as parking lot roofs, noise cancelling barriers, dam walls, alongside railway and road embankments, avalanche barriers or on wastewater treatment facilities.</p>
<p>Benefits and challenges</p>	<p>Solar PV on existing infrastructure allows for an efficient double use of land, combining renewable electricity production with the original function of the infrastructure. However, the deployment of PV systems is not authorized on all infrastructures due to safety concerns related to the primary use of the infrastructure. Special circumstances may also require additional safety measures, e.g., to support the weight of the panels on roofs and barriers, which increases complexity and the cost of the installation.</p>
<p>Current production</p>	<p>There are several pilot projects in Switzerland with PV on infrastructure, such as the parking lot roof of a shopping mall in Aigle (1.8 MWp), or on the dam wall of the Muttssee (2.2 MWp). The total amount of electricity produced is nonetheless negligible for the Swiss supply.</p>

Performance indicators

<p>Production potential by 2035</p>	<p>Approximately 8 TWh of electricity could be produced per year from infrastructure PV by 2035 in Switzerland, including parking lot roofs, road and railway infrastructure. This would be equivalent to 14% of the annual Swiss electricity production in 2022 (58 TWh).</p>
<p>Specific yield</p>	<p>In the Swiss Midlands and pre-Alps, where most usable infrastructure is located, a solar PV panel with a capacity of 1 kWp can produce 1150-1350 kWh of electricity per year. PV on infrastructures in the Alps can have up to 25% higher yield.</p>

<p>Winter electricity production</p>	<p>For the most common types of infrastructure PV, such as parking lot roofs, the share of winter electricity production is about 30%. This makes infrastructure PV less suitable for closing the winter electricity gap. Only in exceptional cases, where panels can be installed at high altitude in a vertical position, can winter production be higher (e.g., dam walls, avalanche barriers).</p>
<p>Electricity costs</p>	<p>Electricity costs for infrastructure PV broadly range between 7-30 ct./kWh, strongly depending on the type of infrastructure, its accessibility, the sun exposure, and size of the installation. In general, infrastructure PV tends to be more expensive than rooftop PV because of the more diverse and difficult conditions for installation and maintenance.</p>
<p>Grid integration and storage</p>	<p>Infrastructure PV must be connected to the grid and in most cases the existing grid can be used to ensure access. In some cases, the electricity can be consumed on site by the infrastructure service itself (e.g., charging stations for electric vehicles, wastewater treatment facilities, train stations), but storage solutions may be necessary to secure reliable and flexible supply.</p>
<p>Maintenance</p>	<p>Access to sites may not always be possible without interruptions in the daily operation of the primary infrastructure due to safety risks (e.g., PV systems along roads and railway). Some locations may also be more exposed to factors that increase the need for maintenance because they damage or lower the efficiency of panels, such as fine dust from traffic accumulating on the panel surface or stone chipping.</p>
<p>Expected lifetime and end-of-life</p>	<p>The expected lifetime of solar PV systems on infrastructure is about 30 years, but exposure to harsh weather conditions may wear our panels more quickly and shorten their lifetime. The removal of the PV systems typically does not cause any permanent damage to the infrastructure.</p>
<p>Impacts on land use and natural landscapes</p>	<p>The installation of infrastructure PV requires no additional land use, as PV systems are integrated into already built environments. Similarly, the visual impacts on natural landscapes are very low.</p>
<p>Impacts on environment and biodiversity</p>	<p>Infrastructure PV typically does not directly interfere with the surrounding ecosystems and natural habitats of flora and fauna. The negative impacts on the environment and biodiversity are therefore minimal.</p>

PV in agriculture (Agri PV)

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Technology description

Agri PV refers to the installation of solar PV in agricultural environments. Applications include installing solar PV on greenhouses or mounting PV on the ground alongside permanent cultures or on pastures and croplands.

Benefits and challenges

Agri PV allows for efficient double use of land by combining food production with renewable electricity production. It can provide beneficial impacts for agriculture, such as by protecting crops against hail, frost, and drought or by providing shading for grazing animals. This can increase the productivity of the lands, as well as reduce water consumption, erosion and the use of pesticides and plastics in agriculture. However, to ensure that electricity production does not compromise food production, the current Swiss law only allows agri PV where no negative impacts arise on agricultural yields. This effectively limits the application of agri PV to crops that are resistant and tolerant towards reduced sunlight (e.g., berries, leafy vegetables). Site-specific conditions may further pose practical constraints, such as ensuring accessibility of tractors and harvest machines to fields and inside greenhouses.

Current production

Except for a few demonstration plants, agri PV is not used on a large scale in Switzerland today.

Performance indicators

Production potential by 2035

The technical potential of agri PV is very large, with production estimates reaching up to 30 TWh, but this is likely not feasible in the mid-term. More realistically, approximately 10 TWh of electricity could be produced per year from agri PV by 2035 in Switzerland, including permanent cultures, pastures and farmlands that are very close to a grid connection (less than 100 m). This would be equivalent to 17% of the annual Swiss electricity production in 2022 (58 TWh).

Specific yield

In the Swiss Midlands and pre-Alps, where most of agricultural land is located, a solar PV panel with a capacity of 1 kWp can produce 1150-1350 kWh of electricity per year. This is up to 25% lower than for solar PV located in the Swiss Alps.

<p>Winter electricity production</p>	<p>The share of electricity produced during the winter has been estimated at around 30%, making agri PV less suitable for closing the winter electricity gap. However, this largely depends on the location of the solar PV panel and whether it is deployed with a horizontal (e.g., on greenhouses) or vertical tilt (e.g., ground-mounted in fruit plantation).</p>
<p>Electricity costs</p>	<p>Electricity costs for agri PV in Switzerland have been estimated to be 8-10 ct./kWh. Electricity costs are thus generally estimated to be lower than for rooftop PV, thanks to the economies of scale of larger installations.</p>
<p>Grid integration and storage</p>	<p>Large agri PV systems must be connected to the grid which can be challenging for remote locations and may require the construction of additional grid infrastructure. Where possible, the electricity can also be consumed directly on site, e.g. for agricultural purposes. However, due to the relatively small electricity demand in agriculture, grid integration or storage solutions are necessary to balance between daily production and demand.</p>
<p>Maintenance</p>	<p>Access to sites typically does not pose a problem thanks to existing road infrastructure, even for more remote locations. The maintenance of agri PV installations can however be challenged by the limited space at sites, especially due to the presence of crops and/or supporting structures that should not be damaged during interventions.</p>
<p>Expected lifetime and end-of-life</p>	<p>The expected lifetime of agri PV systems is about 30 years. Ground-mounted systems are typically exposed to harsher weather conditions (e.g., strong winds) than those installed on greenhouses and may shorten the lifetime of panels. At the end of life, sub-structures such as cemented platforms can either be reused for new panels or removed, which may cause some temporary damage to the ground. With proper measures, land can typically be restored to its initial condition.</p>
<p>Impacts on land use and natural landscapes</p>	<p>The installation of agri PV requires no additional land use, as PV systems are integrated into existing farmland. Impacts on natural landscapes are therefore very low. The visual impacts on areas such as grasslands and pastures, which may be perceived as natural landscapes, can be minimized by choosing colors for the PV panels that match the environment.</p>
<p>Impacts on environment and biodiversity</p>	<p>The overall impacts of agri PV on the environment and biodiversity are not yet fully understood, as both positive and negative impacts can occur. On the one hand, it has been demonstrated that agri PV conserves water in the soil and reduces erosion by giving additional protection against extreme weather (e.g., hail, strong wind). On the other hand, the additional shading effect from panels can potentially impact the microclimate of soils in a manner that disrupts the required humidity levels, temperature, and availability of nutrients for microorganisms or small insects. Negative effects can be limited by choosing locations that are already intensively used by farming and have low initial biodiversity (e.g., greenhouses).</p>

Floating PV

Technology description

Floating PV refers to installing solar PV panels on water bodies such as on artificial lakes or reservoirs. This is done with the help of anchored platforms that carry the PV panels on the water surface.

Benefits and challenges

Floating PV moves electricity production from land to water and thus helps reduce the use of land. At high altitudes, floating PV systems are especially advantageous thanks to the increased sunlight and the cooler temperatures which increase the efficiency of systems and electricity transmission. When installed on reservoirs serving hydropower plants, the floating panels reduce evaporation, preserving more water in the reservoirs that subsequently increases the electricity production from the hydropower plant. The deployment of floating PV in Switzerland is currently restricted to artificial lakes and reservoirs. Local conditions may also render some water bodies unsuitable or difficult to operate, such as due to poor sun exposure, natural hazards (e.g., strong winds, snow) or large water level variations.

Current production

There is one large-scale floating PV system in Switzerland, located in the reservoir of Lac des Toules (Valais). It produces electricity for almost 300 households (620 000 kWh/year) and covers a surface of 2 240 m².

Performance indicators

Production potential by 2035

Approximately 1 TWh of electricity could be produced per year from floating PV by 2035 in Switzerland (counting only artificial lakes and dams). This would be equivalent to 2% of the total electricity produced in 2022 (58 TWh).

Specific yield

In the Swiss Alp, where most artificial lakes and dams are located, a solar PV panel with a capacity of 1 kWp can produce around 1550 kWh of electricity per year. This is up to 25% more than for solar PV located in the Swiss Midlands.

<p>Winter electricity production</p>	<p>Floating PV systems at high altitude show a rather balanced seasonal generation, with 40% of the annual electricity produced during the winter. This makes floating PV on dams and artificial lakes rather suitable for closing the winter electricity gap.</p>
<p>Electricity costs</p>	<p>Electricity costs have been estimated to range between 12-30 ct./kWh, largely depending on project-specific conditions. Electricity costs for floating PV are thus generally higher than for rooftop PV but can reach comparable levels under optimal conditions.</p>
<p>Grid integration and storage</p>	<p>Sites for floating PV typically do not have any electricity demand on-site and must be connected to the grid. When built on reservoirs next to hydropower plants, the necessary grid and storage infrastructure is typically available and can be easily integrated. For artificial lakes without existing infrastructure, new grid access must be built.</p>
<p>Maintenance</p>	<p>Floating PV systems can face challenging conditions for maintenance due to their location on water. This includes accessing the construction by boats and having additional security constructions for protecting electric cables in the water. For sites at high altitude, the accumulation and evacuation of snow can be managed by installing panels in a vertical position. In winter, the panels do not need much maintenance and activities can be limited to only inverters and transformers. The ice coverage of lakes typically does not pose a challenge for the maintenance of the panels.</p>
<p>Expected lifetime and end-of-life</p>	<p>The expected lifetime of floating solar PV panels is about 30 years, but harsh weather conditions may wear out installations faster. The floating structure itself can last up to 60 years, only requiring a replacement of the solar panels at mid-life. At end-of-life, the removal of the anchoring structures may cause some damage to the lake bottom or the shore, but surroundings can be restored to their initial conditions with proper measures.</p>
<p>Impacts on land use and natural landscapes</p>	<p>The installation of floating PV on dams and artificial lakes requires very little additional land use and the impacts on natural landscapes are therefore very low. However, as dams and artificial lakes may be perceived as part of natural landscapes, floating PV can in some cases be considered to visually impact surrounding landscapes (e.g., alpine environments).</p>
<p>Impacts on environment and biodiversity</p>	<p>Floating PV systems have in some cases been found to reduce aquatic plant growth and oxygen levels below the panels. However, such negative impacts can be considered small in artificial lakes and dams, since these water bodies have a very low initial biodiversity and ecosystem function. Floating PV has virtually no impact on terrestrial ecosystems because of its very limited additional land use.</p>

Ground-mounted alpine PV

Technology description

Ground-mounted alpine PV refers to the installation of ground-mounted solar PV in mountainous environments, such as on open fields or moderately steep and south-facing slopes.

Benefits and challenges

Alpine PV takes advantage of a range of favorable production conditions that only occur at high altitudes, including higher sunlight, lower cloud coverage, stronger reflection rates from snow cover, lower temperatures and higher system efficiencies for panels and electricity transmission. Overall, this allows alpine PV to produce more electricity than is possible at lower altitudes, with the difference in production being especially significant in winter. However, the availability of alpine PV sites is often challenged by their remote location and the lack of infrastructure (e.g., roads, electricity grid). Locations with a natural or cultural heritage value may not be suitable for deployment.

Current production

There are no large-scale alpine PV installations currently in operation in Switzerland. However, several sites are being explored for deployment and are under review, such as in the cantons of Valais or Grisons.

Performance indicators

Production potential by 2035

The production potential of ground-mounted for the mid-term is yet to be analyzed more in detail. Approximately 8 TWh of electricity could be produced per year from alpine PV by 2035 in Switzerland. This would be equivalent to 14% of the electricity production in 2022 (58 TWh).

Specific yield

A solar PV panel in the Swiss Alps with a capacity of 1 kWp can produce around 1550 kWh of electricity on an annual basis. This is up to 25% more than for solar PV located in the Swiss Midlands.

<p>Winter electricity production</p>	<p>Alpine PV can produce up to 50% of the electricity during winter and thus reach a balanced generation profile between the seasons. This makes ground-mounted alpine PV very suitable for closing the winter electricity gap.</p>
<p>Electricity costs</p>	<p>Available estimations project electricity costs of alpine PV to range between 10-15 ct./kWh. Electricity costs are generally estimated to be lower than for rooftop PV, thanks to the economies of scale of larger installations as well as higher electricity production.</p>
<p>Grid integration and storage</p>	<p>In the case of remote and previously unused sites for alpine PV, new infrastructure must be built which makes grid integration more costly. The need for additional infrastructure can (partially) be lowered by choosing sites in proximity to hydropower plants or ski resorts. In such cases, the electricity can also be directly used for on-site demand or nearby activities (e.g., skiing lifts).</p>
<p>Maintenance</p>	<p>Alpine PV faces harsh weather conditions and natural hazards such as strong snowfall and landslides which can complicate maintenance activities, especially for remote locations with difficult access (e.g., steep slopes). The accumulation and evacuation of snow can be managed by installing panels in a vertical position.</p>
<p>Expected lifetime and end-of-life</p>	<p>The expected lifetime of alpine PV systems is about 30 years, but harsh weather conditions (e.g., strong winds) and natural hazards (e.g., rockfalls) may wear out the installations faster. At end-of-life, sub-structures such as cemented platforms can be reused for new panels or removed, which may cause some temporary damage to the ground. With proper measures, land can typically be restored to its initial condition.</p>
<p>Impacts on land use and natural landscapes</p>	<p>In most cases, the installation of large-scale and ground-mounted alpine PV requires additional land use and therefore also has an impact on natural landscapes. The visual impacts can be minimized by choosing colors for the PV panels that match the environment, by choosing sites with existing infrastructure, such as ski resorts, or less visited areas.</p>
<p>Impacts on environment and biodiversity</p>	<p>The overall impacts of ground-mounted alpine PV on the environment and biodiversity are not yet fully understood, as both positive and negative impacts can occur. On the one side, the deployment of solar PV may disturb the local flora and wildlife by fragmenting the ecological habitats of species, such as through the construction of fences and roads. Shading effects from panels may additionally adversely impact the microclimate of soils by influencing temperature, humidity, and irradiation levels. However, positive effects may equally occur, resulting in improved water conservation in soils and reduced erosion.</p>

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References and attributions for images and photos

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Figure 2: “Swiss electricity mix” by Sanni Kunnas (*left*) and “[Photovoltaic power potential](#)” by Solargis and World Bank Group (*right*), used under [CC BY 4.0 DEED](#)

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